

Unlocking Novel Potential: The Human Microbiome as a Reporter and Predictor of Health

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Document control sheet

Deliverable number:	4.3
Deliverable responsible:	UCC
Editor:	X
Press releases:	X

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Document Revision History			
Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
V0.0	30/04/2024	First draft	
V0.1	13.05/2024	Second draft	

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Executive Summary

The human microbiome represents the collective communities of microorganisms and the structures and elements they use to interact with their environments, which includes various sites in and on the human body. Microbiomes play important roles in many aspects of human health, including immune education, drug and nutrient metabolism and resistance to pathogen colonisation. Research is showing associations between the human microbiome and an increasing number of diseases, ranging from digestive to neurological disorders. However, despite these insights into the role of the microbiome in human health and disease, **defining a ‘healthy’ microbiome remains a challenge in research**. This is in part due to the complexity and variation present within human microbiomes and is compounded by a lack of comparability and coordination of existing microbiome research. As such, the **full impact of the microbiome is yet to be achieved**, and has resulted in limited clinical translation, unclear regulatory guidelines for industry and risk of consumer exploitation and misinformation. Addressing the central issues facing microbiome research in Europe, ranging from specific technical considerations to fundamental approaches to microbiome research, is essential to fully capitalise on the translational applications of the microbiome in general practice and clinical settings to match the growing citizen interest in microbiome-targeted products and therapies.

This document represents an outcome of the EU-funded Human Microbiome Action project, part of which focuses on outlining a pathway towards defining a ‘healthy microbiome’. With this White Paper, we encourage policymakers across Europe, both within national governments and EU institutions, to recognise the importance of the human microbiome in research programmes and health policies, as well as the need for a larger and more collective approach to address the central challenges facing human microbiome research in Europe.

Action within the following areas is needed to coordinate and expand existing microbiome research to maximise the potential for diagnostic and therapeutic utility:

- Orientation of research funding towards microbiome epidemiology to support development of centralised, longitudinal, representative, population-scale microbiome studies.
- Promotion of standardisation and accessibility of microbiome data and metadata to improve comparability and translational impact of microbiome research.
- Delineation of regulatory pathways to both structure innovation and favour developments serving public health interests towards better management of chronic disease epidemics.

Introduction

What is the Human Microbiome?

Various sites in and on the human body are home to distinct communities of microorganisms referred to as microbiomes. **The term microbiome encompasses the microbes themselves (the microbiota), including bacteria, archaea, viruses, and fungi, as well as their genetic material, molecules they produce, and the microbial structures and elements they interact with in their environment**¹. While the gut microbiome represents the most active area of research, there are many different niches within the human body where microbial communities exist, such as the skin, mouth and vagina².

The microbiota act as important drivers of human health, where they perform a variety of beneficial functions for the host, such as providing resistance to colonisation by environmental microbes including pathogens and education of the immune system, as well as many niche-specific functions. For example, the gut microbiome provides digestive capabilities that the human genome lacks³, produces essential vitamins and metabolites, such as short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs)⁴, and through various pathways involving immune, nervous and endocrine systems, can communicate with organs such as the brain to shape social and cognitive behaviour⁵. **Beyond these beneficial functions, distinct microbial signatures are being associated with a growing number of diseases; many of which are non-communicable diseases (NCDs) that represent an overwhelming majority of the burden of diseases in the EU**⁶. For example, several studies have cited the association between colorectal cancer progression and the composition of the gut microbiome⁷. Reduced diversity of the skin microbiome has been linked with conditions such as atopic dermatitis⁸, while oral microbiomes have been associated with various disease states ranging from cardiovascular to Alzheimer's disease⁹.

Although the importance of human microbiomes is increasingly recognised, unlocking its full potential remains limited by the vast degrees of variation both between and even within individuals. Within individuals, microbiome composition and function can dramatically differ over time and depending on the body site in question. Remarkably, the diversity and variability of genetic features within the human microbiome is far greater than that of the human genome, with microbial genes thought to outnumber host genes by a factor of 100¹⁰. However, compared to the relatively fixed nature of human genomes, change is the only constant for the human microbiome. Indeed, microbiomes adapt and change dramatically over time, at both short timeframes (day-to-day¹¹) or across the lifespan¹². **Between individuals, microbiomes are highly personalised and are shaped by unique combinations**

of many distinct influences, such as mode of delivery at birth, diet, geography, age and even circadian rhythm ¹³. Microbiome alterations include changes in microbial community composition (changes in species diversity, relative and absolute abundances of different microbes) and function (changes in the type and number of compounds produced which can impact other microbes and the host).

As a result of this variation, there is a need to identify the expected or most desirable features of human microbiomes that maximise health benefits in the largest group of people. While research has made some progress towards a workable definition of a 'healthy' microbiome, overall, there has been very little translation of microbiome research into validated clinical or commercial solutions. Defining clear, reproducible and practicable microbial markers of health, which can account for variability, is essential to both develop reference ranges for human microbiomes needed to support translation of microbiome research, and in protecting consumer rights and health. To reach this goal, improved coordination and cohesion of microbiome research in Europe is critical to address these challenges and to capitalise on the impact of microbiomes in health and disease.

From Pasteur to Present: Microbiome Research in Europe

From the first direct observations of microbes present in humans by Antonie van Leeuwenhoek, Europe has played a central role in the development and evolution of microbiome research. Pioneering discoveries from figures like Pasteur, Koch and Metchnikoff highlighted the important roles of microbes in human health and disease, while newer breakthroughs in sequencing and other multi-omics technologies towards the turn of the century have been pivotal in helping to uncover the complexity, diversity and interconnectivity of human microbiomes. More recent developments, such as the MetaHIT project ¹⁴, which established an extensive reference catalogue of microbial genes and genomes present in the European gut, have laid the groundwork for the recent explosion of interest in human microbiomes.

Today, Europe remains at the forefront of microbiome research and innovation and continues to be a main contributor to existing public human microbiome data ¹⁵. This expertise has developed from investment at an EU and national level, providing funding for projects that expand knowledge of the human microbiome, while also supporting development of research infrastructure and dedicated microbiome research centres across Europe. **Despite an acknowledgement of the need for broader collaborative approaches and projects as part of the Horizon Europe programme, considerable fragmentation and decentralisation of microbiome research continues** ¹⁶. This represents a growing concern for the field as the shift towards larger and more complex datasets underlies a need for increasingly centralised, standardised and accessible approaches to microbiome data collection, analysis and comparison.

Advances in sequencing technologies and continued expansion and refinement of microbial reference genome databases have launched microbiome research into an era of ‘big data’. This is due to not only lower sequencing costs facilitating sampling of increasing numbers of people but is also compounded by the need for integration with many different data types, such as longitudinal data, multi-omics, and a heightened focus on functional analysis and modelling adding further complexity ¹⁷. These technological advances, supported by a European research landscape supporting high-risk, high-reward research and innovation, have facilitated major breakthroughs in our understanding of the features and importance of human microbiomes. These include discoveries of the importance of the microbiota-gut-brain-axis for social and stress behaviours ^{5,18}, identification and reconstruction of thousands of human-associated microbial genomes ¹⁹ and the ability of the gut microbiome to shape efficacy of cancer treatments ²⁰.

In recent years, increased funding of microbiome research has facilitated a pronounced shift towards assembling larger cohorts, evident with successful European initiatives such as FINRISK ²¹, the Flemish Gut Flora Project ²² and the Dutch Microbiome Project ²³, and continuing with recently launched projects, such as Le French Gut (<https://lefrenchgut.fr/>), aiming to sequence the gut microbiomes of 100,000 people in France, as part of the emerging Million Microbiomes from Humans Project. While research has primarily focused on profiling microbiomes and discerning their associations with health, there is a growing need for deeper mechanistic insights to determine the specific applications of the microbiome for human health. However, to maintain European excellence in microbiome research, upscaling and continuing current initiatives and fostering greater coordination is crucial to enhance the impact of research outcomes. In addition to continuing to increase EU investment in microbiome research, centralising and restructuring funding to maximise the potential applications of the microbiome and progress towards a shared definition of a ‘healthy’ microbiome must be a key priority going forward.

Overcoming Challenges in Microbiome Research

The core problem facing microbiome research is that despite increased funding for microbiome research in the EU, the full potential of the human microbiome has yet to be actualised. This is in part due to the complex dynamics and variation of human microbiomes but is further complicated by a fragmented research landscape and a lack of consensus for approaches to study design, methodologies and analysis. These challenges, ranging from specific technical considerations to the fundamental question of a healthy microbiome, represent areas of microbiome research deserving priority attention in European research, innovation and health policies.

Unknown Microbial Species, Strains and Functions

With the emergence of powerful next-generation sequencing technologies supporting the recent explosion in microbiome research, progress has been made in the identification and classification of diverse members of human microbiomes. **However, many microbes currently remain either undetectable by existing techniques or represent unclassified ‘dark matter’ sequences, which leaves us without a complete understanding of the full spectrum of human microbiome compositions** ^{24–27}. Existing approaches to microbiome sampling have predominantly focused on bacteria, with considerably less known about other members of human microbiomes, such as viruses, fungi and archaea. These non-bacterial components have been shown to play fundamental roles in determining the overall community structure of human microbiomes and as putative markers of host health status ²⁸. Compared to the more cost-efficient 16S rRNA sequencing, which is largely specific to bacteria, metagenomic sequencing uses the whole genomes present in a sample to identify not only the different bacterial and non-bacterial species present but can also provide a more in-depth characterisation of specific strains of species and their associated functional capacities. This holds considerable potential as microbiome functionality shows more stability and is more conserved across individuals, and in cases of vaginal inflammation, has proven to be a more accurate predictor of disease than microbiome composition ²⁹.

However, despite these advancements in microbiome sequencing tools, available metagenomic data from publicly accessible databases and repositories is limited for classification of non-bacterial reference genomes and does not sufficiently support functional annotation of the majority of microbial species or strains ²⁶. As such, there is a need to not only prioritise research utilising metagenomic sequencing but to combine this with sustained support of microbiome reference databases and development of analytical tools in order to coordinate efforts to address existing knowledge gaps in microbiome research.

Limited Standardisation and Representation within Microbiome Data

While addressing existing research gaps will provide opportunities to potentially identify novel microbial predictors or reporters of health, without corresponding changes to current approaches and funding of microbiome research, the full impact of any discoveries will not be realised. Considerable variation of existing approaches to overall microbiome study design, sampling and analysis has greatly contributed to disparity between studies and consequentially to the non-comparability or generalisability of previously acquired results³⁰. While standardisation represents a widely stated goal for the field, reaching consensus and determining the optimal methodology and techniques to employ across studies remains a challenge^{31,32}.

While efforts have been made to develop standardised protocols for microbiome sample processing, sequencing and analysis, including those produced from the European-led IHMS (International Human Microbiome Standards) project^{33,34}, many of these initiatives are not financed to allow for continuous updating and expansion of protocols to account for technological developments in the field. In addition to differences in how microbiome research is conducted, there are also clear inconsistencies in how microbiome research is reported. **At a minimum, there is a need for improved reporting of microbiome data and metadata (typically any information separate from the microbial data itself, such as a participant's medical history or how/when a sample was collected and analysed) to better support comparison and meta-analysis within microbiome research**^{35,36}. Specifically, reaching consistent and accepted minimal standards for reporting clinical metadata represents one aim of the Human Microbiome Action project, as it represents the pathway to explore and account for the influences of microbiome variation. This is a central issue facing microbiome research, as variation is currently mostly unexplained with individual differences in known factors, such as medication, age or dietary measures thought to account for only around 15% of total variation in gut microbiome composition²².

In addition to moving towards standardisation in microbiome research, development of diverse representative datasets is essential to develop generalisable markers of health that can be adjusted for and account for influences such as age or geographic location. This is evident from research where geographic variation within a single region of China severely limited the generalisability of 'healthy' microbial reference ranges and accuracy of disease models³⁷. Rather than assuming that discoveries from an independent study specific to one area can be generalised nationally or even globally, microbiome research must prioritise the need to develop predictions based on comparison between and within larger-scale studies to identify and experimentally validate any signatures of health or disease. To do so, disparities in microbiome research must be addressed, as these have resulted in existing databases not being truly representative at global scale.

Overall, while Europe is over-represented in microbiome research owing to a history of consistent and large-scale research funding, even within Europe inequalities exist with eastern European countries comparatively underreported ¹⁵ (Figure 1). **Ensuring that microbiome research is both generalisable and representative must be an active and specific priority for funding bodies both at a European level and globally** ³⁸. Where addressing existing research gaps will provide opportunities to potentially identify novel microbial predictors or reporters of health, without corresponding changes to current approaches and funding of microbiome research, the full potential impact of any discoveries will not be realised. However, even by supporting projects that expand our knowledge of the components present within human microbiomes and facilitate comparison of variation of microbiomes across different populations, to identify clear outcomes for research the fundamental question of how we define a healthy microbiome must be addressed.

Figure 1. Global Microbiome Representation (Reproduced from Abdill et al., 2022)

No Clear Definition of a ‘Healthy’ Human Microbiome

Although it is widely accepted that health is complex, can change over time and is specific to each individual, microbiome research typically takes a more simplified approach for the sake of practicality. **The focus of research so far has been to characterise a healthy host-associated microbiome, where a ‘healthy’ microbiome is one that is present in a ‘healthy’ host. However, deciding who qualifies as healthy in research is not straightforward** ³⁹. Typically, this is achieved through case-control studies that define health as the absence of disease, or by applying exclusion criteria at recruitment, such as BMI or medication usage. However, even within ‘healthy’ groups, considerable variation persists due to influences beyond disease, like pet ownership or geography ⁴⁰. Additionally, as studies are typically selected based on medical history, ‘healthy’ groups may be genotypically predisposed, undiagnosed or in pre-clinical stages of various health conditions which cross-sectional case-control studies are unable to account for ^{41,42}. Human microbiomes also have their own separate ecological measures of health, such as diversity, resistance and resilience, which often prove challenging to quantify but hold potential as independent predictors and monitors of host health ⁴³. This raises the question of how we measure a ‘healthy’ microbial ecosystem, and how to incorporate this into a definition of a ‘healthy’ microbiome.

Changes in microbiome diversity or gene richness are routinely used in research and commercial tests as a shorthand measure of how ‘healthy’ a microbial community is ⁴⁴. **However, these measures alone are often too broad to provide specific or informative insights into potential impacts of a given microbiome on the host.** Additionally, measures of diversity do not always perfectly correlate with features of host health, with higher diversity of gut microbiomes in non-industrial populations attributed to both a ‘loss of species’ occurring in response to Western dietary patterns ⁴⁵ as well as reflecting rates of infection by helminths ⁴⁶. Newer tools, such as the Gut Microbiome Health Index (GMHI) ⁴⁷, have been developed to provide a simple and interpretable measure of disease risk based on existing data of the most differentially abundant species between individuals with or without clinically diagnosed disease. These measures show more predictive ability than microbiome diversity but are limited by existing data gaps and reliance on data from a predefined set of diseases, utilising a binary case-control classification to predict the risk of developing disease. Clustering approaches have also shown some utility as a means to determine microbial features associated with health, through simplification of the spectrum of microbiomes in human health into discrete categories ⁴⁸. Community state types (CSTs) for the vaginal microbiome have been used to correlate with bacterial vaginosis risk ⁴⁹, while enterotypes for the gut microbiome, originally proposed from data from the European MetaHIT project, have shown some success in associating community composition with systemic inflammation ^{50,51}. However, whether such measures are accurate enough to translate towards clinical diagnostics remains an area of debate as, unlike blood types or genetic markers, microbiome composition and functionality are not discrete or fixed.

Longitudinal sampling, where participants are sampled across multiple time points, provides a means to monitor the complex dynamics of human microbiomes ⁵²⁻⁵⁴. **Unlike the majority of current microbiome research, which provides a snapshot of the microbiome at a single point in time, longitudinal studies can be used to report how the microbiome at a given point in time can predict the clinical fate of an initially healthy person as long as the health system records relevant events over time.** However, such studies must be linked and comparable with larger datasets to improve validity and impact of findings to account for variation in health over time, in response to influences and to support the use of the microbiome as a predictor of future health status ⁵⁵. At this point in time, research can determine that a certain species or feature of the microbiome is linked with a given disease, but in looking ahead to maximise the potential of human microbiomes, we must determine whether these identified associations can predict development of the disease before it progresses to clinical detection ⁵⁶.

Lost in Translation: Consequences of Microbiome Research Gaps

From technical and methodological differences to fundamental questions about how we define a healthy microbiome, the need to address challenges in microbiome research is becoming increasingly apparent and is starting to be recognised at an EU level, with funding calls specific to coordinating microbiome research supporting projects such as Human Microbiome Action and MicrobiomeSupport as part of the Horizon2020 programme. As the microbiome represents a rapidly growing area of clinical, commercial and citizen interest, increased and sustained action is needed to ensure that the current excitement surrounding microbiome research does not outpace what evidence can reasonably support⁵⁷. Already, gut microbiome therapeutics have been approved for the treatment of recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* infection (rCDI)^{58,59} but lacks consistent classification, regulation and approval within the EU. The demand for over-the-counter microbiome therapies, including probiotics and prebiotics, is continuing to grow with the probiotics market alone estimated to be worth USD 78.91 billion in 2024 and to increase to USD 113.43 billion by 2029. **Despite these successes, overall, existing research gaps have restricted progress towards validated references for a 'healthy' microbiome, contributing to limited clinical translation, unclear regulatory guidelines for industry and risk of consumer exploitation and misinformation.** The following points represent some of the key areas directly impacted by existing microbiome research gaps, ranging from innovation and development of novel microbiome-based diagnostics and therapeutics to regulation and communication of microbiome research and products to consumers.

From Innovation...

- Development of **predictive diagnostics** is progressing due to advances in machine learning approaches to analyse increasingly complex and expansive microbiome datasets. However, these approaches are only as effective as the data they are trained on. Without comparable population-specific and longitudinal reference data, current models show difficulty in determining generalisable and reliable predictors of health status or disease³⁷.
- A lack of consensus on how to best use microbiome data to stratify individuals limits application of microbiome-based **precision medicine and nutrition**³⁹. Similar to difficulties in creating reliable tools to predict disease development, microbiome data is not yet able to act as a **companion diagnostic** to match patients with the most applicable interventions.

- Without a clear reference for a ‘healthy’ microbiome, **clinical trials** for interventions targeting human microbiomes lack validated quantifiable outcomes independent to measures of host health ⁶⁰.
- For **microbiome-based therapies** such as faecal microbiota transfer (FMT), donors are classified as ‘healthy’ based on screening for and exclusion of potential pathogens as well as exclusion of any chronic disease or perceived risk thereof, based on extensive questionnaires. However, the full potential benefits or risks of transfer of a given microbiome remain unclear. The absence of validated reference ranges for ‘healthy’ microbiomes still limits the robust screening of donor microbiomes totally unlikely to drive predisposition to specific diseases independent of clinical presentation at the time of donation ⁶¹.

...To Regulation

- As microbiome research is yet to fully translate to widespread clinical use, **direct-to-consumer (DTC) solutions** represent the most accessible option for microbiome testing and ‘tailored’ modification. However, DTC microbiome testing currently lacks analytical and clinical validity, with considerable variation in how companies conduct and analyse samples to determine a ‘healthy’ microbiome in the absence of centrally validated reference standards ⁶².
- The complexity of microbiomes and novelty of microbiome research means that there is currently no **centralised regulation** for classification of microbiome-based treatments or testing services in Europe ⁶³. This discourages development of more expensive but potentially clinically relevant microbiome diagnostics and therapeutics in favour of unregulated DTC services.
- Without a clear reference for a ‘healthy’ microbiome, existing research is unable to provide sufficient evidence to match the current **hype surrounding microbiome research**. A lack of consensus within the field leaves the public vulnerable to misinformation and exploitation ⁶⁴.

Toward an Integrated Approach to Microbiome Research in Europe

To maximise the impact of microbiome research, future studies will need to strike a delicate balance between accounting for the complexity and variability of human microbiomes while still supporting development of simple, robust, and quantifiable microbial markers of host health. Addressing the current challenges facing microbiome research necessitates a shift from case-control studies to approaches prioritising increased sample size, representative recruitment of participants without exclusion criteria, and longitudinal analysis. These priorities align with the emerging concept of microbiome epidemiology ⁶⁵, following in the footsteps of landmark studies such as the European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition (EPIC-Europe) ⁶⁶ and the Framingham Heart Study ⁶⁷. **Within Europe, the recent emergence of population-scale microbiome cohorts, such as the Estonian Microbiome Cohort (EstMB) ⁶⁸ and the Flemish Gut Flora Project (FGFP) ²², have already provided new insights into potential microbial markers and signatures of health, while the Dutch Microbiome Project has recently identified core features of the gut microbiome of healthy individuals ²³.** Supporting regional and national initiatives like these represents a strategic direction for European microbiome research. However, this will require funding pathways such as Horizon Europe to evolve to accommodate maintenance of population-scale longitudinal cohorts alongside smaller, high-risk, high-reward projects.

As seen with the open-access American Gut Project ⁴⁰, these large cohorts can act as centralised and living databases of microbiomes that can explore the full spectrum of health across multiple parameters. They also can serve as validation cohorts for comparison with other population-scale studies and smaller independent studies. **Leveraging existing data from larger cohorts improves comparability and generalisability of microbiome research while providing sufficient statistical power for smaller ‘satellite’ studies linked to a centralised core cohort.** With this integrated approach, ‘satellite’ studies could also be used to complement discoveries from the core cohort to achieve mechanistic insights into specific associations observed in the larger core cohort ¹⁰. Additionally, development of comprehensive reference databases for European microbiomes would better support integration of microbiome data into risk assessments for evaluating the impacts of compounds and products on human health, fitting with strategies recently proposed under the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) focused on dietary compounds and the gut microbiome ³⁶.

Figure 2. Satellite Model for Microbiome Research (Adapted from Joos et al., currently under review)

However, realising the full potential of microbiome epidemiology for European research requires accounting for the cost of developing and maintaining these large initiatives, as well as balancing the need for comparable and accessible microbiome data with data protection regulations⁶⁹. Integrating microbiome-specific research with existing cohorts, as seen with the Dutch Microbiome Project²³ as an offshoot of the existing LifeLines cohort, can reduce overall costs of project recruitment and coordination. With epidemiological studies being prospective and longitudinal in nature, incorporation of microbiome sampling can also support longitudinal analysis needed to accelerate development of microbiome-based predictive diagnostic tools. In addition to supporting initiatives that aim to foster standardisation of microbiome research and reporting, ensuring that data and metadata from core cohorts are accessible, or specifically open access, is fundamental to maximise the impact of this approach. Efforts such as the European Digital Health Space (EDHS)⁷⁰ hold potential as a pathway to support transfer and accessibility of microbiome data for research while ensuring adherence to the requirements of existing data protection regulations for highly sensitive health data. Overall, addressing the challenges currently facing microbiome research in Europe will require an updated approach to both maximise the impact of existing discoveries and lay the groundwork for future research. Embracing microbiome epidemiology and development of population-scale, representative and longitudinal cohorts offers a promising pathway to unlock the full potential of human microbiomes for European research while addressing logistical and regulatory challenges.

Policy Recommendations

Human microbiomes are complex microbial communities present throughout humans that contribute to overall well-being through functions such as immune education, drug and nutrient metabolism and resistance to pathogen colonisation. Capitalising on the full scope of opportunities contained within microbiomes is crucial going forward to identify new approaches to monitor and predict human health. However, clinical translation remains limited by the considerable variability of microbiomes between and within individuals and lack of consensus on what defines a 'healthy' microbiome. Despite Europe's role as a global leader in microbiome research, fragmentation within the current research landscape requires a more centralised and standardised approach to handle the growing complexity and scale of microbiome studies in the era of big data.

At a European and national level, policymakers can make significant differences to address these challenges and maximise the impact of the rapidly growing field of microbiome research. Throughout this White Paper, we have explored how the challenges in defining a 'healthy' microbiome represent a central issue facing research to date. To unlock the potential of the human microbiome as a reporter and predictor of health, Human Microbiome Action emphasize prioritizing centralised population-based approaches at the core of microbiome research initiatives and recommend the following actions:

Funding of Microbiome Research

- Through Horizon Europe and other mechanisms, direct future microbiome research funding towards initiation of **population-based cohorts** to determine the features of human microbiomes that correlate with health (for example by developing a Horizon Europe funding call to establish large-scale microbiome cohorts across Europe and development of a centralised European metagenomic reference database).
- Reform funding structures to support development and longevity of **longitudinal microbiome studies**.
- Promote a **pan-European and representative approach** towards microbiome research, by;
 - Developing microbiome research initiatives and infrastructure in widening countries through the Widening Participation and Spreading Excellence actions under Horizon Europe;
 - Prioritising previously under-represented populations (such as ethnic minorities, migrant communities and lower socioeconomic status participants) in existing and future initiatives.

Application of Microbiome Data

- Partner with scientific bodies, such as the newly formed European Microbiome Centres Consortium (EMCC), and other multi-stakeholder initiatives to develop **centralised and standardised protocols** for data collection and analysis to ensure comparability of microbiome data.
- Formally recognise and encourage application of the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) **principles for data management** in microbiome research.
- Move forward on implementation of the **European Digital Health Space (EDHS)** to;
 - Support the use of health metadata in microbiome research;
 - Extend the EDHS to formally include microbiome data itself as a form of health data in the EU.
- Develop a coordinated approach to ensure sufficiently **annotated, complete and comprehensive clinical metadata** for use in microbiome research through;
 - Establishing a set of minimal requirements and standardised identifiers for reporting metadata in microbiome research at an EU level;
 - Encouraging integration of microbiome studies with existing national health records;
 - Promoting further investment, through Digital Europe and other initiatives, to support integration of digital health technologies and personal devices with microbiome data.

About Human Microbiome Action

This White Paper represents one of the outputs from part of the [Human Microbiome Action](#) (HMA) project focused on defining a healthy microbiome. HMA is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) supported by the EU Horizon 2020 funding programme. This project aims to keep Europe at the forefront of microbiome research and innovation while maximising its impact by ensuring coherence and harmony in the way microbiome research is and will be performed. In bringing together leading EU and international players, HMA is collectively developing international synergies for research and knowledge transfer in the microbiome field at EU and international levels and provides instruments to support a robust usage of microbiome knowledge to promote human health and to tackle the epidemics of chronic diseases. This project involves 17 European project partners in a unique collaboration between scientific experts, medical doctors, the private sector, editors, funding agencies and regulatory agencies.

In February 2024, HMA launched the European Microbiome Centres Consortium (EMCC) as a collective of institutions and research centres within the EU actively involved in microbiome research. The overarching aim of the EMCC is to provide guidance and advice on how to advance microbiome science to tackle some of the major challenges and accelerate the science-based translation of microbiome research to stakeholders including citizens, policymakers, and industries.

The EMCC will follow from the work of the HMA project through actions including:

- Harmonizing standards for microbiome research to ensure robust and reliable methodologies and practices within the field.
- Promoting microbiome regulatory frameworks in Europe and advocating for the acknowledgement of scientific consensus and requirements in the field of microbiome research.
- Raising awareness and educating the public and healthcare professionals about the importance of the human microbiome in health and disease.

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**Human
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964590